

Interpretation of COVID-19 Swab Statistics

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Abstract

Each day during the current COVID-19 pandemic many countries report the number of diagnostic swabs performed and the number of positive cases found. These data help to predict the immediate course of the public health emergency. However, their interpretation is non-trivial because the more tests performed, the greater the number of positive cases that will be found. In this document we propose a method for interpreting the data and we apply it to data from Italy.

Introduction

The current COVID-19 pandemic is overwhelming the health services of many countries. One of the countries most affected in Europe is Italy, a country for which fairly reliable data are available. Daily statistics are provided by the Dipartimento della Protezione Civile and are freely available for download [1]. The relevant file is “dpc-covid19-ita-regioni.csv”. Figure 1 plots the daily number of inpatients (the column labelled “totale_ospedalizzati” in the CSV file) summed for all regions. The numbers are now rising again, but will this continue?

As in most countries, widespread testing using nasal swabs is performed in Italy each day to identify infected persons. The results of these tests also help to monitor the effectiveness of various Government interventions intended to suppress progression of the pandemic. Figure 2 plots the number of newly positive cases each day (the column labelled “nuovi_positivi” in the file, summed for all regions). Notice that there is a considerable weekly variation in the counts. This reflects a significant reduction in testing and reporting at weekends. Notice also that the daily number of positive results is much larger now during the second wave of the pandemic compared to that during the first. This reflects a greater availability of testing and screening. Consequently a larger number of mild and asymptomatic cases are being detected together with an inevitable number of false positives. While a useful indication of the severity of the pandemic, the number of positive swab results is only a crude and biased approximation to the actual prevalence of COVID-19, many cases of which are asymptomatic. The daily number of new cases can be interpreted only in the light of the number of swabs actually performed.

Figure 1: *Number of COVID-19 inpatients in Italy in the period 24/02/2020 to 05/03/2021.*

Figure 2: *Daily number of new cases of COVID-19 in the period 24/02/2020 to 05/03/2021.*

Number of Daily Swabs

The cumulative number of swabs being performed in each region is listed in the column labelled “tamponi”). The number of swabs performed each day is calculated by subtracting the cumulative number for the particular region on successive days. Unfortunately, there are a few anomalies. For example, on 17/12/2020 the cumulative number for Piemonte appears to have undergone a reset. This leads to a negative number of calculated swabs for that particular day. We handle this anomaly by estimating the number of swabs performed on 17/12/2020 to be the average of those on 16/12/2020 and 18/12/2020. We call this correction procedure *method 0*.

Region	Date	Cumulative	Difference	Adjusted
Piemonte	15/12/2020	1784446	18330	18330
	16/12/2020	1801939	17493	17493
	17/12/2020	1586358	-215581	13493
	18/12/2020	1595851	9493	9493
	19/12/2020	1606272	10421	10421

In other cases, an error appears to have occurred when transcribing the cumulative number on a particular date. For example, on 30/03/2020 the calculated daily number for Emilia-Romagna is negative because it appears that the cumulative number that day was erroneously low. We deal with this type of transcription error by averaging the calculated negative number of swabs with that calculated for the following day. This is equivalent to replacing the rejected cumulative number with the average of its predecessor and successor. We call this procedure *method 1*.

Region	Date	Cumulative	Difference	Adjusted
Emilia-Romagna	28/03/2020	52991	5193	5193
	29/03/2020	52991	0	0
	30/03/2020	50990	-2001	771
	31/03/2020	54532	3542	771
	01/04/2020	58457	3925	3925

Similarly, if a calculated daily number is negative because it appears that the cumulative number on the previous day is too high then we average the calculated negative number with that for the previous day. Similar corrections proved necessary for the number of new cases each day, some of which were negative. A complete list of the various corrections is to be found as an appendix in Tables 1 and 2 on pages 21 and 22.

Figure 3 plots the daily number of swabs performed in Italy, calculated by summing the adjusted numbers for all regions. This confirms the hugely increased number of swabs now being performed. It also confirms that the marked weekly variation in new cases is indeed due to reduction in testing at weekends. The weekly oscillation in number of swabs performed is more marked than that of new cases presumably because the latter has been partially smoothed by variable delays in reporting.

Interpretation

The results are difficult to interpret in absolute terms without knowing how many of the swabs are actually re-tests and, if some are, whether initially positive and initially negative cases have the same probability of being re-tested. However, interpretation is also confounded by the inevitable fact that the greater the number of tests that are performed, the greater the number of positive cases that are found. It therefore makes sense to normalize the number of new cases by the number of swabs performed each day. Figure 4 plots the number of new cases as a proportion of swabs performed. This corresponds more closely to the number of inpatients. However, the apparent passing of the second main peak must be interpreted in the light of a still changing number of daily swabs being performed. This is difficult to do without knowing and taking into account the selection criteria for performing the swabs. In the rest of this document we propose a method for overcoming this obstacle. However, first we should eliminate as far as possible the weekly oscillations.

Figure 3: *Daily number of swabs performed in the period 24/02/2020 to 05/03/2021.*

We filter weekly oscillation from the number of new cases and the number of daily swabs in the conventional manner by using a centrally-aligned, seven-day, moving-average filter. We first apply the logarithmic transformation $\log(x+1)$ to stabilize cycle amplitude. We use the method described in [2] to handle the first three days and the last three days, thus avoiding any truncation of the time series. We apply the inverse logarithmic transformation after smoothing. Figures 5 and 6 show the results. Using these smoothed values to calculate the number of new cases as a proportion of the number of swabs we obtain a correspondingly more stable trajectory (Figure 7). We see that after a small peak following the festive season, the number of new cases each day is apparently rising again, but does this reflect a true reversal?

Figure 4: *Daily number of newly positive cases expressed as a proportion of swabs performed in the period 24/02/2020 to 05/03/2021.*

Figure 5: *Smoothed daily number of new cases of COVID-19 in the period 24/02/2020 to 05/03/2021.*

Figure 6: *Smoothed daily number of swabs performed in the period 24/02/2020 to 05/03/2021.*

Figure 7: *Smoothed daily number of newly positive cases expressed as a proportion of the smoothed number of swabs performed in the period 24/02/2020 to 05/03/2021.*

A Severity Relation

Let the counts each day be a pair (c, s) in which c is the smoothed number of newly positive cases and s is the smoothed number of swabs performed. As a technical condition, always satisfied in practice, we assume that $c \leq s$. Now we regard the results as worse than those on another day precisely when both the following conditions are met:

1. The absolute number of newly positive cases is at least as great.
2. The number of newly positive cases expressed as a proportion of the number of swabs performed is strictly greater.

The dual requirements mean that any increased number of positive results could not simply be a consequence of performing more swabs as that would not increase the proportion of newly positive cases; if anything, it would tend to lower the proportion because testing would be extended to less overtly symptomatic cases. Conversely, any increase in the proportion of newly positive cases could not be due to a reduction in the number of tests, concentrating them on the more overtly symptomatic: this would miss some positive milder cases. Notice that both these arguments are still valid even if there are a significant number of false positives. Worse results thus imply that there are more infected persons in the population.

Accordingly let us define a relation on daily counts that reflects their relative gravity. For any pairs (c_0, s_0) and (c_1, s_1) ,

$$(c_0, s_0) \sqsubset (c_1, s_1) \iff c_0 \leq c_1 \wedge c_0 s_1 < c_1 s_0 \tag{1}$$

Expressed informally, the above definition is

$$(c_0, s_0) \sqsubset (c_1, s_1) \text{ holds precisely when } c_0 \leq c_1 \text{ and simultaneously } c_0 s_1 < c_1 s_0$$

If the relation does not hold, it does not follow that it necessarily holds in the reverse direction. The two days may in fact be incomparable because exactly one of the two conditions is satisfied by each day relative to the other. Thus, technically, the severity relation is a “strict partial order” because it follows immediately from its definition that it is irreflexive, antisymmetric, and transitive.

Example

For example, here are the smoothed counts (rounded to the nearest integer) on three consecutive days which we will refer to as D_{17} , D_{18} , and D_{19} .

Day	Date	New Cases (c)	Swabs (s)	Proportion (c/s)
17	12/03/2020	2318	9863	0.2351
18	13/03/2020	2505	11723	0.2137
19	14/03/2020	3009	12471	0.2413

Now, D_{19} is worse than both the preceding two days because there were more newly positive cases even when normalized by the number of swabs. However, days D_{17} and D_{18} are incomparable as although the absolute number of newly positive cases on day D_{18} is greater than on day D_{17} , the reverse is true when normalized by the number of swabs. Represented diagrammatically, the ordering of these three days in terms of their severity is as follows.

A Severity Score

A simple score for ranking each day according to its severity is the number of days that it is strictly worse than divided by the total number of days with which the severity ordering is decidable. Let the number of days in the database be n and let the days in chronological order be D_0, D_1, \dots, D_{n-1} where each day is a pair of parameters (c, s) . (At the moment $n=376$). Let the severity score S_i on each day D_i be defined as follows.

$$S_i = \frac{\#\{j : 0..n-1 \mid D_j \sqsubset D_i\}}{\#\{j : 0..n-1 \mid D_j \sqsubset D_i \vee D_i \sqsubset D_j\}} \quad (2)$$

Expressed informally, the above definition is

$$S_i = \frac{\text{The number of days } D_j \text{ for which } D_j \sqsubset D_i}{\text{The number of days } D_j \text{ for which } D_j \sqsubset D_i \text{ or } D_i \sqsubset D_j}$$

The score is undefined in the event that the denominator is zero. This occurs, for example, if no swabs are performed on day D_i . This eventuality must be handled explicitly in some suitable way, for example, by excluding such days. However, this did not arise for the data under present consideration.

Notice that the relative severity score establishes a total ordering which, although weaker, is consistent with the severity relation itself. It is easily shown that for any i and j ,

$$D_i \sqsubset D_j \implies S_i < S_j \quad (3)$$

Figure 8 plots the severity score. Notice that after falling to zero by about day 125, it started to rise again on about day 140 (13/07/2020). This was the start of the Summer season, restrictions had been largely lifted, and a considerable amount of social interaction occurred again. It reached a second peak on about day 270 (20/11/2020) before falling again. The

Figure 8: *Severity (S_i) of the pandemic in the period 24/02/2020 to 05/03/2021.*

aftermath of the festive season saw a temporary worsening, but for the last week or two it has been steadily rising again.

Notice that the severity score of a day is potentially determined by the entire database and, in general, is affected by both earlier and later days. However, the relatively limited testing capability during the first wave meant that the daily new cases were fewer in number than in the second wave but greater when expressed relative to the number of swabs performed. Figure 9 plots each day in the two dimensions. Days up to day 125 (= 28/06/2020) are plotted in green and later ones in red. Day 125 was chosen as it seems to be at about the mid-point of the remission between the two waves. Two days are comparable when a line drawn through their points on the scatter plot has a positive gradient. Therefore we see that the improvement in testing resources means that the second wave is incomparable to the peak of the first wave although it is still comparable to the initial and final phases of the latter. Furthermore, the

severity plot evolves dynamically as more days are recorded. For example, Figure 10 shows the plot by day 173 (15/08/2020). It is a little different to the corresponding part of the more recent plot.

Figure 9: Scatter plot of smoothed number of newly positive cases expressed as a proportion of the smoothed number of swabs performed against the absolute (smoothed) number of new cases in the period 24/02/2020 to 05/03/2021.

Figure 10: *Severity (S_i) of the pandemic in the period 24/02/2020 to 15/08/2020.*

Regional Comparisons

The severity on each day for any given region is calculated by a straightforward modification of Equation 2. The numerator and denominator are adjusted to range over all the region-days, that is to say every day for every region. Thus the particular region-day is compared to all other region-days; in doing so we exclude as inadmissible any region-days on which no swabs were performed. Figure 11 plots the results for a few selected examples: Lombardia; Abruzzo; Calabria; and P.A. Trento. Save for the last day in Abruzzo, the severity in all four regions appears to have been generally rising for the last week or two. This is reflected, for example, by a recent increase in the number of inpatients in Abruzzo (Figure 12).

Figure 11: *Severities (S_i) of the pandemic in selected regions in the period 24/02/2020 to 05/03/2021.*

Figure 12: *Number of COVID-19 inpatients in Abruzzo in the period 24/02/2020 to 05/03/2021.*

Scatter Plots

Figure 13 shows a scatter plot of all the region-days on which at least one swab was performed. There were 7894 such region-days in total. For clarity we have made the distribution more uniform by replacing each parameter (c or c/s) with its zero-indexed rank, normalized to the range $[0, 1]$ by dividing by the highest rank. Since this is a monotonic transformation, it does not affect the procedure for comparing pairs of points.

Figure 13: *Scatter plot of normalized ranked pairs for all regions in the period 24/02/2020 to 05/03/2021.*

Example

Figure 14 gives an example, Abruzzo on 15/08/2020, showing how the other region-days determine its severity. There were 5004 region-days that were strictly worse (coloured red) and 1668 that were strictly better (coloured green). Thus the severity score is

$$\begin{aligned} S_{\text{Abruzzo, 15/08/2020}} &= \frac{1668}{1668 + 5004} \\ &= 0.25 \end{aligned}$$

Figure 14: Scatter plot of normalized ranked pairs for all regions in the period 24/02/2020 to 05/03/2021 showing those comparable to Abruzzo on 15/08/2020.

Decidability

The greater the number of other region-days a given region-day can be compared with, the more meaningful its severity score. Accordingly, we define the *decidability* of a region-day as the proportion of all other region-days with non-zero swabs to which it can be compared. Figure 15 plots the cumulative relative frequency of decidabilities for all such region-days. The median decidability is 0.7877. So, the severity statistic is determined by comparison with about 79% of the other region-days.

Figure 15: *Cumulative distribution of decidabilities for all region-days in the period 24/02/2020 to 05/03/2021.*

Discussion

The severity score is a general guide to the relative progression of the pandemic. It anticipates and predicts the positive or negative gradient of the number of inpatients (Figure 1) and hence the changing pressure on hospital services. Although it is harder to interpret in absolute terms than the conventional reproduction number [3], the latter entails various modelling assumptions, is complicated to calculate, and is normally expressed with often wide error bounds. By contrast, the severity score is straightforward and requires only the daily numbers of new cases and swabs performed. Furthermore, it is insensitive to the presence of false positives because the ordering is in terms of relative counts. Despite its simplicity, the severity score appears to be a useful monitor. For example, it was already clear by the mid-Summer public holiday on 15/08/2020 that the pandemic was intensifying again (Figure 10), long before significant additional restrictive measures were reapplied. Moreover, it now appears that recovery from the second wave has been reversed and the situation is worsening markedly (Figure 8).

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References

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Region	Date	Reported	Adjusted	Method
Piemonte	26/02/2020	0	0	
	27/02/2020	-1	4	1
	28/02/2020	9	4	
Piemonte	08/03/2020	153	72	
	09/03/2020	-10	72	2
	10/03/2020	103	103	
Liguria	29/02/2020	23	3	
	01/03/2020	-17	0	2
	02/03/2020	-3	0	
Liguria	01/03/2020	-17	0	
	02/03/2020	-3	0	2
	03/03/2020	2	2	
Marche	18/05/2020	11	4	
	19/05/2020	-3	4	2
	20/05/2020	2	2	
Campania	11/06/2020	3	3	
	12/06/2020	-229	2	0
	13/06/2020	0	0	
Basilicata	06/05/2020	3	3	
	07/05/2020	-16	1	0
	08/05/2020	-1	1	
Basilicata	07/05/2020	-16	1	
	08/05/2020	-1	1	0
	09/05/2020	0	0	
Calabria	16/04/2020	38	10	
	17/04/2020	-18	10	2
	18/04/2020	20	20	
Sicilia	01/03/2020	5	2	
	02/03/2020	-2	2	2
	03/03/2020	0	0	
Sardegna	03/05/2020	4	1	
	04/05/2020	-2	1	2
	05/05/2020	1	1	
Sardegna	24/05/2020	0	0	
	25/05/2020	-2	0	0
	26/05/2020	0	0	
Sardegna	08/06/2020	0	0	
	09/06/2020	-1	0	0
	10/06/2020	0	0	

Table 1: *Adjustments for anomalies in case counts in various regions.*

Region	Date	Cumulative	Difference	Adjusted	Method
Piemonte	16/12/2020	1801939	17493	17493	0
	17/12/2020	1586358	-215581	13493	
	18/12/2020	1595851	9493	9493	
Valle d'Aosta	14/03/2020	231	42	42	1
	15/03/2020	230	-1	28	
	16/03/2020	287	57	28	
Valle d'Aosta	22/06/2020	18239	847	99	2
	23/06/2020	17589	-650	99	
	24/06/2020	17700	111	111	
Valle d'Aosta	02/12/2020	61373	460	460	0
	03/12/2020	54987	-6386	377	
	04/12/2020	55280	293	293	
Lombardia	25/02/2020	3700	2237	873	2
	26/02/2020	3208	-492	873	
	27/02/2020	3320	112	112	
Friuli Venezia Giulia	18/03/2020	4958	0	0	1
	19/03/2020	4052	-906	3	
	20/03/2020	4964	912	3	
Emilia-Romagna	29/03/2020	52991	0	0	1
	30/03/2020	50990	-2001	771	
	31/03/2020	54532	3542	771	
Marche	24/01/2021	671124	8569	8569	0
	25/01/2021	659081	-12043	6594	
	26/01/2021	663699	4618	4618	
Abruzzo	26/07/2020	127354	3358	580	2
	27/07/2020	125155	-2199	580	
	28/07/2020	125542	387	387	

Table 2: *Adjustments for anomalies in swab counts in various regions.*